

The Evolving United States Space – Enabled Reconnaissance – Strike Complex: Theory, Practice and Challenges

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Abstract

This article explains ways in which robust space capabilities have become an indispensable foundation for success in employing modern airpower. It considers how military space capabilities fit into conceptual models for modern warfare and uses these models to review evolution of the global reconnaissance-strike complex that first emerged in 1991 during Operation Desert Storm. It discusses specific ways space capabilities support each step in the find, fix, track, target, engage, and assess “kill chain” and outlines the many space systems the United States has deployed to modernize and improve these capabilities. The article concludes by addressing critical current space security challenges including growth in orbital debris, increasing worldwide deployment of counterspace capabilities, increasing efficacy of commercial space systems and the role of the billionaire “space barons” that control these systems, the threat of a nuclear detonation in low-Earth orbit, and the prospects and implications of the United States developing and deploying proliferated space-based interceptors capable of boost-phase intercepts as called for in president Trump’s Iron Dome for America Executive Order.

Keywords

Anti-satellite (ASAT), John Boyd, Brilliant Pebbles (BPs), Reconnaissance-Strike Complex (RSC), Find-Fix-Track-Target-Engage-Assess (F2T2EA) Kill Chain, David Lupton, Nitze Criteria, Resilience, John Warden, Low-Earth Orbit (LEO), Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO), Barry Watts.

1. Conceptual Models.

Many analysts today believe warfare’s character is changing significantly, moving away from traditional focus on annihilation or attrition of fielded forces toward seeking to induce strategic paralysis among enemy decision makers – approaches variously described as hybrid, new generation, or simply new ways of war. These discussions also include debates about whether we are currently amid a revolution in military affairs (RMA) that renders existing means of warfare subordinate or obsolete. Whether we are currently witnessing a true RMA or simply a significant transformation, space capabilities clearly make some of the most important contributions to enabling more effective and efficient use of airpower.

In the mid-1970s the Soviet General Staff began to postulate that advances in precision munitions, wide-area sensors, and computerized command and control would fundamentally change warfare and potentially make conventional weapons as effective as nuclear weapons. Marshall Nikoli Ogarkov, Chief of the General Staff from 1977-84, championed these concepts and encouraged work to combine these capabilities, labeling the concept a “reconnaissance-strike complex” (RSC).¹ Many analysts believe the decisive airpower victory of coalition forces in Operation Desert Storm (ODS) heralded the emergence of a nascent but operational RSC. ODS airpower operations included stealth, long-range precision strikes, parallel attack of many targets simultaneously, denial of enemy commanders’ ability to communicate with fielded forces, and direct attack of enemy decision makers rather than fielded forces. The comprehensive military space capabilities the United States had deployed during the Cold War enabled the emergence of this RSC. U.S. Air Force Chief of Staff General Merrill McPeak labeled the conflict the “first space war” to emphasize the highly significant and comprehensive contributions of space capabilities to the coalition’s victory.²

Recent American airpower theorists and their heirs have built on the decisive victory in ODS to refine conceptual models for effective and efficient use of modern airpower. John Boyd originally developed his energy-maneuvering and observe-orient-decide-act (OODA) concepts from visual dogfighting, but scores of subsequent analysts have applied OODA analysis to everything from business to politics; in the military context, space capabilities can provide critical observation and orientation knowledge to apply the OODA model worldwide. John Warden conceived of the enemy as a system consisting of five concentric rings focused on leadership and moving outwards toward organic essentials, infrastructure, population, and fielded forces. Warden postulated that airpower could conduct parallel attacks against all five rings simultaneously, could disrupt connections between the rings, and contradicted many traditional military theories by making fielded forces the least important target set.³ Space capabilities again play a critical role under this concept as they are essential for identifying specific targets within each ring and enabling assessment of the effectiveness of airstrikes.

Another important conceptual model for thinking about ways space capabilities can support national security was developed by Air Force Lieutenant Colonel David E. Lupton in his 1988 book, *On Space Warfare*.⁴ Lupton argued there were four schools of thought regarding broad, national-level strategies the United States could pursue in using space to improve its security: sanctuary, survivability, control, and high ground. The first two, sanctuary and survivability, emphasized the ways space capabilities could enhance strategic stability and improve the effectiveness of terrestrial forces. The sanctuary school argued that the primary value of space systems was in providing strategic stability through capabilities including nuclear command and control, missile warning, and national technical means of verification (NTM) for arms control. Adherents to this school argued that capabilities to attack satellites should not be developed because this would undermine strategic stability. The survivability school acknowledged that space capabilities were improving not just strategic stability but also significantly enhancing the effectiveness of tactical military operations. It emphasized that space systems are inherently less survivable than terrestrial forces and should be made more resilient against attacks so they could continue providing some diminished level of support to military operations even during and after attacks. Lupton's other two schools had greater emphasis on space forces and the space domain. His control school called for space to be thought of like other domains where the primary military objective is to gain control over operations in this area. Militaries seek to preserve their freedom of action and deny freedom of action to enemies; in a domain as vast as space it is unlikely that control can be maintained for large areas over extended periods of time. Lupton's final school, high ground, argued that space holds the potential to be the decisive theater of combat operations. Reasoning by historical analogy, the high ground school portends that just as holding the high ground is often the decisive factor in land combat or as airpower often prevails over land and sea forces, in the future, space forces will dominate terrestrial warfare. Lupton argued that the control school should be the basis for U.S. space strategy. Figure 1 summarizes, expands, and updates Lupton's schools by listing the primary value of military space forces, outlining deployment strategies for space systems, showing primary combat missions of space forces, and suggesting appropriate organizational structures for operations and advocacy.⁵

	Primary Value and Functions of Military Space Forces	Space System Characteristics and Employment Strategies	Conflict Missions of Space Forces	Appropriate Military Organization for Operations and Advocacy
Sanctuary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance Strategic Stability Facilitate Arms Control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited Numbers Fragile Systems Vulnerable Orbits Optimized for NTM Verification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Reconnaissance Office (NRO)
Survivability	Above Functions Plus: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Force Enhancement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Terrestrial Backups Commercial and International Augmentation Autonomous Control Attack Warning Sensors Less Vulnerable Orbits Hardening Redundancy Crosslinks Maneuver Space Mission Assurance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Defensive Operations Resilience <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disaggregation Protection Distribution Proliferation Diversification Deception Reconstitution On-Orbit Spares 5Ds: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deception Disruption Denial Degradation Destruction Bodyguards and Convoys 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Force Enhancement Degrade Gracefully 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Major Command or Combatant Command
Control	Above Functions Plus: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Control Space Significant Force Enhancement 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Control Space Significant Force Enhancement Surveillance, Offensive and Defensive Counterspace 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combatant Command, Space Corps, or Space Force
High Ground	Above Functions Plus: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decisive Impact on Terrestrial Conflict Ballistic Missile Defense (BMD) 		Above Functions Plus: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decisive Space-to-Space and Space-to-Earth Force Application BMD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Space Corps or Space Force

Figure 1: Attributes of Military Space Doctrines

2. Evolution of the RSC.

In practice, the U.S. RSC has evolved in many ways and improved significantly since its inception. Figure 2 traces satellite communication throughput to deployed brigades, lists primary air-delivered munitions (PGMs), and provides the number and percentages of PGMs used in various military operations to describe progress in the U.S. RSC during the last 35 years.⁶ Figure 2 captures some of the clearest and most tangible contributions of space capabilities to the RSC, but their overall contributions are more subtle and comprehensive. Most significantly, space capabilities have enabled the United States to move from being able to employ just a small percentage of PGMs to having the ability to use PGMs for every time-critical target worldwide.

Figure 2: Evolution of a Space Enabled Reconnaissance - Strike Complex – The New American Way of War

Military Operation, Duration, and Megabits Per Second (Mbps) Data Delivered from Satellites to Deployed Brigade-Sized Units	Primary Types of Unguided and Precision - Guided Munitions (PGM) Used	Numbers and Percentages of Unguided and PGMs Used
Desert Storm, 1991: Kuwaiti Theater of Operations, 17 Days, 1 Mbps	Unguided Munitions: Multiple Types PGM: Tomahawk (Terrain Contour Matching); Paveway II (Laser), Maverick (Electro -Optical (EO) and Infrared (IR))	Unguided: 245,000 (92%) PGM: 20,450 (8%)
Allied Force, 1999: Serbia, 78 Days, 24.5 Mbps	Unguided Munitions: Multiple Types PGM: Paveway II (Laser), Joint Direct Attack Munition (JDAM) (Global Positioning System (GPS))	Unguided: 16,000 (68%) PGM: 7,700 (32%)
Enduring Freedom, 2001 -02: Afghanistan, 90 Days, 68.2 Mbps	Unguided Munitions: Wind -Corrected Munitions PGM: Multiple Types (Laser, EO/IR, GPS)	Unguided: 9,000 (41%) PGM: 13,000 (59%)
Iraqi Freedom, 2003: 29 Days, 51.1 Mbps	Unguided Munitions: Wind -Corrected Munitions PGM: Multiple Types (Laser, EO/IR, GPS)	Unguided: 9,251 (32%) PGM: 19,948 (68%)
Inherent Resolve (Counter ISIS and Worldwide Counterterrorism), 2014 -19, No Conventional Brigades Deployed	Unguided Munitions: None Reported PGM: Hellfire, Small Diameter Bomb, and Multiple Other Types including Remotely Piloted Vehicle (RPV) Delivered (Laser, EO/IR, GPS, Radar)	Unguided: None Reported PGM: Totals Not Reported (100%)

During ODS, command and command and control of air operations was enabled by a comprehensive air tasking order (ATO). The ATO attempted to coordinate several thousand daily sorties launched by coalition partners to enhance unity of effort against the highest priority target sets and to deconflict air traffic along ingress, egress, and aerial refueling tracks. Production of the ATO required an inflexible 72-hour cycle. The ATO was often several hundred pages long and contained such large files that it could not be electronically transmitted to all coalition airfields throughout the theater of operations. These drawbacks sometimes resulted in not attacking new targets or restriking targets already destroyed because the ATO was not flexible enough to include newly detected targets or account for recent battle damage assessments (BDA). Continuous improvements in space and other capabilities supporting the RSC have enabled far greater flexibility for air operations under the concept of dynamic re-tasking. Instead of operating under an inflexible 72-hour cycle, newer command and control approaches allow sorties to takeoff without assigned targets, proceed to a “kill box,” and attack targets that may have just emerged or those deemed to be the highest priority once the aircraft arrives on station. PGM evolution reflects another specific example of improvements in the RSC. The standard PGM for the past 25 years, the joint direct attack munition (JDAM), normally had a 2000-pound warhead; JDAMs are being replaced with small diameter bombs, which normally carry only a 250-pound warhead, yet can often be employed more effectively and cause less collateral damage than JDAMs.

3. Space Support of the Kill Chain.

Improvements in the RSC are driven primarily by space capabilities that provide critical contributions to joint all-domain command and control, enable time-sensitive targeting, and help compress every link in the terrestrial find, fix, track, target, engage, assess (F2T2EA) kill chain cycle. Finding enemy forces has been a difficult task for militaries throughout history; aircraft revolutionized reconnaissance within a theater of operations and intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance (ISR) collection from satellites has revolutionized it globally. Change detection enabled by sun-synchronous low-Earth orbit (LEO) imagery satellites often provides some of the most important contributions to ISR and enhances understanding of adversary capabilities as they develop over time. Today, pervasive global imagery provided by National Reconnaissance Office (NRO), Department of Defense (DoD), and commercial satellites means that no significant military activities can remain hidden, and if they can be detected, they can be engaged. Nonetheless, it can be challenging to provide ISR that is precise and timely enough to effectively support the most difficult and fleeting strike opportunities.

Fixing involves identifying potential targets from the finding step and geolocating them. In the past, this was sometimes a difficult and time-consuming process; today the Global Positioning System (GPS) enables near-instantaneous geolocation anywhere in the world and makes a critical contribution to the kill chain. Tracking requires maintaining sensor custody of targets as they move. Persistent space imagery can make important contributions in maintaining custody of targets, but it can also be a challenge to fuse together data from various distributed space and non-space sensor networks. Comprehensive datasets of geospatial intelligence collected over decades from space and non-space sources such as digital terrain elevation data can contribute to target tracking in important ways by indicating likely travel routes for military systems and identifying terrain obstacles and areas where they cannot operate.

Targeting is a complex link in the cycle that is enabled by several space capabilities. Most importantly, military satellite communications, and perhaps commercial satellite communications, are usually needed to connect the entire kill chain together and allow commanders to control the operation. Commanders determine target priorities and sequencing, decide what capabilities will be used for engagement, and direct the forces that employ these capabilities. Depending on the time available and sensitivities regarding certain targets, commanders may use decision making tools that provide extremely detailed modeling of weapons effects based on the desired mean point of impact, predicted damage to target, and potential collateral damage.

Engagement is the use of fires against the target, another link in the kill chain cycle in which space capabilities provide essential contributions. The GPS system is again critical in this part of the kill chain, as most munitions use this capability to guide their employment for at least some portion of the engagement. Assessment, the final link in the kill chain is also dependent on space capabilities; this link is sometimes known as BDA. Many of the same capabilities used initially to find targets are used to assess whether the engagement achieved the desired effects. As engagements become increasingly precise and perhaps employ non-kinetic means, it can be difficult to assess whether subtle desired effects were achieved.

4. U.S. Space Systems Contributing to the RSC.

Figure 3 provides current details about the primary space systems supporting the RSC and the orbits used by these systems.⁷ The figure focuses on dedicated military systems, but it is important to emphasize that many space systems today are dual use, meaning they can support both military and civil or commercial applications. Data streams from space systems can support hundreds of thousands or even millions of users simultaneously and are embedded in thousands of important applications worldwide. The GPS is one of the best examples of this dual-use characteristic. GPS was designed for military use, but after the most precise data was made available without any user fees in 2000, it has become a critical infrastructure technology supporting modern digital life in applications worldwide including global telecommunications and financial transactions; today military GPS use is just a small fraction of all use. There is a dashed line in the bottom part of each column in Figure 3: The systems above the dashed line are currently operational, planned systems that are not yet operational are below the dashed line in white, those in yellow were programs of record that were subsequently cancelled. Some of the data in Figure 3 is not specific because many of the space systems the United States operates are classified, this is particularly true for the ISR mission area systems that are operated primarily by the NRO.

Figure 3: Force Enhancement Missions, Primary Orbits, Major Systems				
Environmental Monitoring	Satellite Communications (Satcom)	Positioning, Navigation, and Timing (PNT)	Missile Warning/Missile Tracking/Missile Defense (MW/MT/MD)	Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance (ISR)
Polar Low-Earth Orbit (LEO)	Geostationary Orbit (GEO) and LEO	Medium Earth Orbit (MEO)	Various	Various
Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP) ----- National Polar - Orbiting Operational Environmental Satellite System (NPOESS), Defense Weather Satellite System (DWSS), Electro-Optical/Infrared (EO/IR) Weather System (EWS), Weather System Follow-on Microwave (WSF-M)	Defense Satellite Communications System (DSCS) II, DSCS III, Ultra-High Frequency Follow-on (UFO), Milstar, Global Broadcast System (GBS), Iridium, commercial systems, Advanced Extremely High Frequency (AEHF), Wideband Global System (WGS), Mobile User Objective System (MUOS), Space Development Agency (SDA) satellites ----- Transformational Communications System (TSAT), Enhanced Polar System, Evolved Strategic Satellite (ESS) system	Global Positioning System (GPS) GPS II GPS IIR GPS IIR -M GPS IIF GPS III ----- GPS-Light	Defense Support Program (DSP), Nuclear Detonation Detection System (NDS), Space-Based Infrared System (SBIRS), Hypersonic and Ballistic Tracking Space Sensor (HTBSS) ----- Precision Tracking Space System (PTSS), SDA satellites, Next Generation Overhead Persistent Infrared (OPIR) Polar (NGP) and Geostationary (NGG), MEO satellites	Geospatial Intelligence (GEOINT) Satellites, Signals Intelligence (SIGINT) Satellites, OPIR systems, Space Based Space Surveillance (SBSS), Geosynchronous Space Situational Awareness Program (GSSAP), commercial systems ----- Future Imagery Architecture (FIA), Integrated Overhead SIGINT Architecture (IOSA), Space Radar
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5. Critical Current Space Security Challenges.

As shown in Figure 4, the world is facing exponential growth in the number and total mass of debris objects in Earth orbit.⁸ Given this debris growth and the trend lines, space operations have already become somewhat compromised, and they will clearly become more dangerous, particularly for sun synchronous LEO operations. Without remediation efforts, LEO may even become increasingly unusable. Fortunately, there is widespread global recognition of this problem and there are some important orbital debris mitigation efforts underway such as the U.S. Orbital Debris Mitigation Standard Practices (ODMSP) that can help to at least slow the growth of orbital debris. Reversing the current orbital debris trends, however, will require moving past mitigation guidelines such as the ODMSP toward comprehensive remediation efforts. Unfortunately, effective remediation of orbital debris is bedeviled by the host of technical, fiscal, political, and economic externality challenges that define all “tragedy of the commons” problems. Figure 4 also shows that the largest single source of orbital debris has been destructive anti-satellite (ASAT) testing such as the Chinese DN-1 test in 2007 and the Russian Nudol’ test in 2021. In this context, an important development is the April 2022 unilateral pledge by the United States that it will no longer conduct destructive direct-ascent ASAT tests. As of this writing, more than 10 other states have made similar unilateral pledges; and in December 2022, 155 states voted for a United Nations General Assembly resolution calling for states not to conduct such tests, while China and Russia voted against the resolution and India abstained (these are the only other states that have conducted destructive ASAT tests). Despite current turmoil in international security dynamics, this transparency- and confidence-building approach may be a pragmatic step toward limiting and eventually banning such tests.

Figure 4. Historical increase of the cataloged objects based on data available on 1 March 2022. The three upward jumps in fragmentation debris correspond to (1) the ASAT test conducted by China in 2007, (2) the accidental collision between Iridium 33 and Cosmos 2251 in 2009, and (3) the ASAT test conducted by the Russian Federation in November 2021. More Cosmos 1-408 fragments are expected to be added to the catalog in the coming weeks and months.

A second significant current space security challenge is posed by the rapid growth in counterspace capabilities – an array of increasingly sophisticated and capable means of disrupting or destroying space systems. Some of the worldwide growth in counterspace capabilities comes from the dual-use potential of commercial systems being developed for on-orbit servicing, but this is less worrisome than the wide range of dedicated counterspace capabilities being developed and fielded by China and Russia as shown in Figure 5.⁹ Chinese and Russian counterspace capabilities increasingly challenge the ability of U.S. space systems to support terrestrial military operations and provide assured nuclear command, control, and communications (NC3) capabilities.¹⁰ China’s new Aerospace Force has developed and is now fielding a range of significant and comprehensive counterspace capabilities that go well beyond anything developed by the superpowers during the Cold War including ASATs with direct ascent capabilities to GEO and satellites with rendezvous-and-proximity and robotic arm capabilities in GEO. Russia has long developed doctrine and capabilities to target U.S. satellites, including critical NC3 systems. Thus far, the United States, China, and Russia have appeared unwilling or perhaps unable to contain the rapid growth in counterspace capabilities and the dangerous and destabilizing conditions created by these developments.

Figure 5

A third space security issue is the increasing efficacy of commercial space systems and the role of the billionaire “space barons” that control these systems.¹¹ As illustrated by the stunning initial successes of the Ukrainians in defending their country following the Russian invasion three years ago, the value of commercial space systems in supporting a wide range of military operations has

grown exponentially.¹² These commercial capabilities provide critical information about ground truth in Ukraine, supply communications connectivity that helps coordinate many Ukrainian military operations, and demonstrate that states do not necessarily need to own and operate space systems to use them effectively. The SpaceX StarLink system controlled by Elon Musk is arguably the single most important space capability supporting Ukraine. In the initial stages of the conflict, Musk donated thousands of StarLink receivers to Ukraine, enabled free connection with his communications network that consists of thousands of LEO satellites, and only later charged the U.S. government for these services.¹³ Musk's initial strong support for Ukraine and current seeming reversal raises important questions about the role of private citizens in determining important aspects of American foreign policy.

In a most disturbing scenario, the efficacy of commercial LEO satellites in supporting Ukraine could lead the Russians (or the Chinese in a Taiwan invasion, for instance) to assess that the greatest military effectiveness from the limited use of nuclear weapons would be to detonate just one in LEO. Unfortunately, this disastrous possibility has moved beyond the hypothetical because Russia appears to be on the verge of violating its Outer Space Treaty (OST) obligations by orbiting a nuclear weapon. Article IV of the OST is one of the most specific parts of the treaty and indicates signatories are “not to place in orbit around the Earth any objects carrying nuclear weapons or any other kinds of weapons of mass destruction, install such weapons on celestial bodies, or station such weapons in outer space in any other manner.”¹⁴ In April 2024, Russia vetoed a resolution supported by 13 members of the United Nations Security Council that called on all member states not to develop nuclear weapons specifically designed to be placed in orbit.¹⁵ As shown by Figures 6 and 7, a high-altitude nuclear detonation (HAND) would raise the peak radiation flux in parts of the Van Allen radiation belts by 3-4 orders of magnitude and cause failure in weeks to months of all LEO satellites without specific hardening against this effect.¹⁶ There would be catastrophic and cascading worldwide consequences of such an attack. Failure of LEO satellites would cause about \$500 billion in direct financial damage and the overall economic impact could be losses of over \$3 trillion.¹⁷ An orbital nuclear weapon presents extremely daunting detection, deterrence, and response challenges because there are few effective counters. The world community should address this challenge multidimensionally, including by ensuring that LEO satellites supporting critical infrastructure and safety-of-life functions have appropriate backups and hardening to deal with this threat.

Figure 6
LEO Natural Background Radiation Conditions

Space is a harsh environment that demands some radiation hardening in all satellites.

Figure 7
Post-HAND Radiation

Natural and Enhanced Electron Population
 One Day After Burst Over Korea

HAND raises peak radiation flux in parts of LEO by 3-4 orders of magnitude.

Models indicate that peak flux could remain high for two years at lower latitudes and higher orbital altitudes.

Satellites will accumulate radiation damage much faster than designed for:

- faster degradation of active electronics (communications, attitude control);
- mission failure in a fraction of planned satellite orbital lifetime.

Hardening typical of commercial satellites is insufficient to cope with a post-explosion environment.

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A final and undoubtedly most comprehensive and impactful current space security challenge is raised by planning guidance in “The Iron Dome for America” (now called the Golden Dome) Executive Order (EO) issued by president Trump on 27 January 2025 that includes: “Development and deployment of proliferated space-based interceptors capable of boost-phase intercept.”¹⁸ By the end of March, DoD is to complete initial planning for development and deployment of the comprehensive layered defense system to counter hypersonic, cruise, and

ballistic missiles that is called for in the EO. Trump's EO signals a radical redirection of United States missile defense efforts and represents a far more comprehensive and ambitious defensive system than ever envisioned under president Reagan's Strategic Defense Initiative (SDI) or "Star Wars" program. With the fall of the Soviet Union and end of the Cold War, the United States has never deployed any space-based ballistic missile defense interceptors, and all SDI materials have not yet been declassified, but it remains highly instructive to review the detailed planning DoD conducted for such systems in the late 1980s and early 1990s that is provided in Aaron Bateman's definitive *Weapons in Space: Technology, Politics, and the Rise and Fall of the Strategic Defense Initiative*.¹⁹

In 1988, the Joint Chiefs of Staff (JCS) issued effectiveness criteria for the Phase I Strategic Defense System (SDS) that included having capability to destroy half of the Soviet Union's SS-18 intercontinental-range ballistic missiles (ICBMs) attacking in the first wave and to destroy 30 percent of other attacking systems. Intercepts during boost-phase give defenders the greatest leverage because they have the potential to destroy many warheads with a single shot and this helps explain focus on the SS-18, a very large missile capable of carrying many independently targetable reentry vehicles. The intent of the criteria was to "enhance deterrence by ensuring that the structure of a full-scale attack could be disrupted."²⁰ In June 1990, the Defense Acquisition Board made small, individual LEO interceptors known as Brilliant Pebbles (BPs) the key component of the Phase I SDS. Substituting individual BPs for larger interceptors stored together in LEO "garages" was an important step in reducing the estimated costs for the initial defense system. It also helped make the BP-based system arguably the first defense approach capable of meeting the criteria advocated by Ambassador Paul Nitze: The system should be able to survive attacks against it and still operate effectively and incremental investments in defenses should be more valuable than incremental investments in offensive systems, this second criterion is also known as being cost effective on the margin.²¹ The most detailed planning for the Phase I SDS to meet the JCS criteria called for deployment of 4614 BPs costing \$1.1-1.4 million each, launch costs of \$2-3 billion, and the total cost for the Phase 1 SDS deployment was estimated to be \$55 billion.²² Shortly after these estimates were made, President Bush (41) significantly reoriented the program toward far more limited objectives known as global protection against limited strikes (GPALS). A final aspect deserving of far more study and consideration is addressing all the strategic implications of potentially deploying thousands of interceptors that may have highly significant ASAT capabilities. Detecting, tracking, and targeting a ballistic missile plume is far easier than performing the same functions against a satellite, but it is likely that any large-scale deployment of interceptors will nonetheless have very significant ASAT potential.

6. References

- 1 B. Watts, "The Maturing Revolution in Military Affairs." Available: <https://csbaonline.org/uploads/documents/2011.06.02-Maturing-Revolution-In-Military-Affairs1.pdf>.
- 2 C. Hall and M. Neufeld, "The U.S. Air Force in Space: 1945 to the 21st Century." Available: <https://media.defense.gov/2010/Oct/01/2001329745/-1/-1/0/AFD-101001-060.pdf>.
- 3 D. Fadok, "John Boyd and John Warden: Air Power's Quest for Strategic Paralysis," 1995. Available: https://media.defense.gov/2017/Dec/27/2001861508/-1/-1/0/T_0029_FADOK_BOYD_AND_WARDEN.PDF
- 4 D. Lupton, "ON SPACE WARFARE A Space Power Doctrine," 1998. Accessed: Mar. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/tr/pdf/ADA421942.pdf>.
- 5 P. Hays, "United States Military Space: Into the Twenty-First Century." Accessed: Mar. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/tr/pdf/ADA435077.pdf>.
- 6 T. Mahnken, "Weapons: The Growth & Spread of the Precision-Strike Regime," American Academy of Arts & Sciences, Jul. 2011. <https://www.amacad.org/publication/daedalus/weapons-growth-spread-precision-strike-regime> (accessed Mar. 04, 2025).
- 7 P. Hays, "United States Military Space: Into the Twenty-First Century." Accessed: Mar. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/tr/pdf/ADA435077.pdf>.
- 8 "NASA Orbital Debris Quarterly News." 2024. Available: <https://orbitaldebris.jsc.nasa.gov/quarterly-news/pdfs/ODQNV28i3.pdf>.
- 9 B. Weedon and V. Sampson, "Global Counterspace Capabilities: An Open Source Assessment." Available: https://swfound.org/media/207826/swf_global_counterspace_capabilities_2024.pdf.
- 10 P. Hays and S. Mineiro, "ISSUE BRIEF: Modernizing Space-Based Nuclear Command, Control, and Communications." Accessed: Mar. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/Hays_-Miniero_-Modernizing-Space-Based-NC3-DRAFTJune25v2-2-1.pdf.
- 11 C. Davenport, *The Space Barons*. PublicAffairs, 2018.
- 12 R. Dickey and M. Gleason, "SPACE AND WAR IN UKRAINE: Beyond the Satellites." Accessed: Apr. 23, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.airuniversity.af.edu/Portals/10/AEtherJournal/Journals/Volume-3_Number-1/Dickey_Gleason.pdf.
- 13 W. Isaacson, *Elon Musk*. Simon & Schuster, 2023.
- 14 United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs, "The Outer Space Treaty," UNOOSA, 1967. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introouterspacetreaty.html>.
- 15 "Remarks Before the Vote on a Russia-Drafted UN Security Council Resolution on Outer Space Security." <https://usun.usmission.gov/remarks-before-the-vote-on-a-russia-drafted-un-security-council-resolution-on-outer-space-security/>.
- 16 "High Altitude Nuclear Detonations (HAND) Against Low Earth Orbit Satellites ('HALEOS') DTRA Advanced Systems and Concepts Office," 2001. Accessed: Mar. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://spp.fas.org/military/program/asat/haleos.pdf>.
- 17 P. Hays and S. Mineiro, "ISSUE BRIEF: Modernizing Space-Based Nuclear Command, Control, and Communications." Accessed: Mar. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/Hays_-Miniero_-Modernizing-Space-Based-NC3-DRAFTJune25v2-2-1.pdf.
- 18 "The Iron Dome for America – The White House," The White House, Jan. 28, 2025. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/01/the-iron-dome-for-america/>.
- 19 A. Bateman, *Weapons in Space*. MIT Press, 2024.
- 20 Bateman.
- 21 Bateman.
- 22 Bateman and D. Baucom, "The Rise and Fall of Brilliant Pebbles," vol. 29, no. 2, 2004, Accessed: Mar. 05, 2025. [Online]. Available: <http://highfrontier.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/09/The-Rise-and-Fall-of-Brilliant-Pebbles-Baucom.pdf>.

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